

Individualised stop aggregation: a combined service-supply and demand-usage driven approach

Howard Wong^{*12} and Joseph Fenwick²

¹ Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis, UCL

² Public Transport Service Planning, Transport for London

GISRUK 2025

Summary

The stop-stop origin-destination (OD) matrix for a large multi-modal public transport (PT) network can be computationally challenging to process and analyse efficiently to support land-use and transport planning. We propose a novel hybrid approach that aggregates the PT stops by proximity and by the mobility pattern of each individual smartcard. The new stop groups improve the imputing of missing journey destinations and reduces the size and complexity of the PT OD matrix. It enables better activity location analysis and can be used for longitudinal cohort analysis to study the detailed changes of PT mobility pattern and behaviour across a network.

KEYWORDS: public transport, origin-destination, spatial aggregation, individual, activities

1. Introduction

Studying network OD flow is fundamental to mobility pattern analysis. Urban and transport planners scrutinise OD patterns to make decisions on land-use, service provision, connectivity, and regularity (Zhong et al., 2016), and use linked journeys to infer activity locations and journey purposes (Sari Aslam et al., 2021).

PT networks can consist of hundreds of millions of OD pairs, which is computationally challenging to process and analyse. Grouping these stops simplifies processing and analysis while retaining the essential travel pattern information, and also supports the inference of boarding or alighting stops from automatic fare collection (AFC) smartcard transactions.

The trip generation stage of the classic four-stage transport demand model partitions a study area into traffic analysis zones (TAZ) which are meant to contain homogeneous demand attraction and generation. However these zones often use administrative boundaries along roads, and stops on opposite sides of the road can be in separate TAZes. Therefore we need another spatial aggregation method.

We propose a hybrid approach that considers both the supply network and the observed demand for stop grouping. It first uses hierarchical clustering to group PT stops using walking distances. Then it considers the origin and destination stop usage pattern by individuals to expand the stop groups to cater for their use of nearby stops. This groups stops serving the same locality to reduce the number of spatial units whilst retaining the spatial positioning of the PT stop. It respects individual usage patterns but maintains a comparable geography to compare between users.

We believe this novel hybrid grouping is unique. This is a complementary technique to the PT mobility analysis toolkit in the literature to handle increasingly complex mobility datasets from smartcards and

* howard.wong.18@ucl.ac.uk

potentially mobile devices. The method has been implemented by (Fenwick et al, 2024) to infer home / work locations and journey purpose from AFC data. We expect this method to be beneficial for analysis of trip chaining, interchange, activities between journeys, home/work/frequently-visited locations and location function.

2. Methodology

Different routes and directions can be served by proximate but separate stops in series along or on the opposite side of the road (Lee et al., 2012). But these stops essentially serve the same locality and provide interchange between services (Hofmann and O’Mahony, 2005). In a large PT network, there can be a choice of nearby stops where a traveller regularly starts and finishes journeys, including some that are further away but offer a more convenient route. Diverse preferences and behaviours deserve a more individualistic representation of the locality for different travellers. Hence a stop grouping can focus the mobility OD analysis between localities, abstracting from the flows of individual stops.

Existing stop grouping methods in the literature are based on land-use or OD flows. Some are designed for within-route rather than network OD (McCord et al., 2012) and some groups have large numbers of stops (Luo et al., 2017) that do not suit detailed mobility analysis or location inference. Moreover, none can be tailored to reflect the individual travellers’ stop usage pattern.

Our hybrid approach considers both the physical position of the PT stops and the usage of them by individuals. It clusters the stops into groups and supergroups, then designates the supergroups according to users’ mobility patterns. Hierarchical clustering groups proximate stops based on walking distances, which helps to avoid cross-river groups. We identify the neighbouring groups for each stop group by distance between centroids, then iterate through all groups to create an overlapping set of base supergroups. Each group can be a member of one or multiple base supergroups.

Figure 1 The polygons are the groups containing different stops (red dots). The group SE19003, outlined in red here, is associated with other groups to form 5 supergroups (outlined in thick blue).

Having created the set of base supergroups, the travel pattern for each smartcard is assessed to assign a set of individualised non-overlapping supergroups. We extract origin and destination stops for completed journeys for each card, and count origin and destination events for each stop. Event counts are then aggregated to the levels of groups and base supergroups. As each stop group may be a member of multiple supergroups, we reduce the overlapping base supergroups to non-overlapping supergroups for each card by selecting the supergroup with the most events out of all the base supergroups that the group is a member of, leaving each group associated to one supergroup only. When inferring whether an activity arrival and a departure are in the same locale, we now use the supergroups instead of individual stops or stop groups. This gives a higher likelihood for the supergroups of successive journeys to match. Once we have identified the locations of the activities between PT journeys for each card, we can analyse the activities, such as inferring home and work locations and their visitation regularity.

3. Data and results

We applied this method to the PT stops and demand in London. We obtained the coordinates of all the active bus stops, trams and rail stations¹ as of November 2023, covering around 20655 stops. The street

walking distance of 600m was used to cluster the PT stops with the hierarchical clustering with Ward method and average linkage, and Euclidean distance of 500m to identify neighbouring groups for base supergroups.

The observed PT journeys are sourced from internal AFC system within Transport for London (TfL) for November 2023. To observe the impact on activity location inference, we focus on the cards that have at least 3 journeys within the study period.

The clustering yield 3430 stop groups, with the mean intra-group between-stop distance of 317m and the mean inter-group between-centroid distance of 478m. The minimum number of stops in a group is 1, maximum 27, mean 5.94 and median 5. With the 500m Euclidean distance between group centroids, 53% of groups have neighbours to form supergroups with. Out of these supergroups, most are formed by 2 groups and the maximum has 7 groups.

For a specific date, there are 8.03 million journeys recorded. Out of the possible 410 million stop-stop OD among all the stops, there are 1.49 million OD that have non-zero demand with sparsity of 0.36%. Conversely, there are 12 million possible group-group OD out of the 3430 groups, of which 0.77 million has non-zero demand. The group OD sparsity is 6.37%, making the OD matrix 18 times more concentrated than using individual stops. Intra-group journeys make up 0.3% of all journeys.

4. Discussions and conclusions

Studying travel behaviour from mobility data in an urban PT system can be complex. Travellers' choices of stops, routes and modes is affected by preferences and service availability. In this paper, we proposed to group proximate PT stops according to walking distance and usage by individuals. The grouping allows for choices and changes of routes and modes, which inform service planning and investigation of behavioural change when services change.

Grouping the stops has significantly reduced the number of analysis units and sparsity in the OD matrices. Instead of grouping stops by land use or OD flows, we group by proximity across the PT network. This retains the spatial integrity and enables the study of end-to-end PT multi-modal, multi-leg movements which can be generalised to other mobility datasets.

Utilisation of movement data allows us to create individualised locations of supergroups for each card to accommodate a small degree of journey spatial irregularity. This significantly improves activity location inference with better matches of preceding destination and succeeding origin, and the quality of activities for longitudinal analyses.

The paper focusses on spatial grouping of journeys. Fenwick and colleagues (2024) demonstrated an application of this stop groups and supergroups method to infer home locations and journey purposes. Additional applications are being prepared for PT route change and service reliability case studies to analyse the change in PT mobility pattern.

References

- Fenwick, J., Wong, H., Levi-Kallin, S., 2024. Overcoming population bias: pathways to enhance smartcard data with home location and trip purpose information. European Transport Conference presentation.
- Hofmann, M., O'Mahony, M., 2005. Transfer journey identification and analyses from electronic fare collection data, in: Proceedings. 2005 IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems, 2005. Presented at the Proceedings. 2005 IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems, 2005., pp. 34–39. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ITSC.2005.1520156>
- Lee, S.G., Hickman, M., Tong, D., 2012. Stop Aggregation Model: Development and Application. Transportation Research Record 2276, 38–47. <https://doi.org/10.3141/2276-05>
- Luo, D., Cats, O., van Lint, H., 2017. Constructing Transit Origin–Destination Matrices with Spatial Clustering. Transportation Research Record 2652, 39–49. <https://doi.org/10.3141/2652-05>

- McCord, M.R., Mishalani, R.G., Hu, X., 2012. Grouping of Bus Stops for Aggregation of Route-Level Passenger Origin–Destination Flow Matrices. *Transportation Research Record* 2277, 38–48. <https://doi.org/10.3141/2277-05>
- Sari Aslam, N., Ibrahim, M.R., Cheng, T., Chen, H., Zhang, Y., 2021. ActivityNET: Neural networks to predict public transport trip purposes from individual smart card data and POIs. *Geo-spatial Information Science* 24, 711–721. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10095020.2021.1985943>
- Zhong, C., Batty, M., Manley, E., Wang, J., Wang, Z., Chen, F., Schmitt, G., 2016. Variability in Regularity: Mining Temporal Mobility Patterns in London, Singapore and Beijing Using Smart-Card Data. *PLOS ONE* 11, e0149222. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0149222>

Biographies

Howard Wong is a part-time PhD candidate in Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis (CASA), University College London, studying public transport origin-destination relationship. He is also a Principal Transport Planner in Transport for London, specialising in data-driven travel behaviour analysis and multi-modal connectivity, and runs an internal PT research programme.

Joe Fenwick has a computational chemistry background and a master’s degree in urban design. He specialises in public transport modelling and analysis, and was awarded “the most innovative use of data” at the 2024 European Transport Conference. His research focusses on data justice, using data to drive more inclusive planning outcomes.